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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****RUTRENDS AND PROSPECTS OF EDUCATIONAL AND
CLINICAL WORK ON THE RESULTS OF THE 10TH
INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM OF CLINICAL AND APPLIED
ANATOMY****Dydykin S.S.¹, Kytko O.V.², Vasil'ev Y.L.³, Shcherbyuk A.N.⁴, Kapitonova M.Y⁵**¹ MD, PhD, Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Head of the Department of Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow² PhD, Associate Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow³ PhD, Associate Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow,⁴ MD, PhD, Professor, I.M. Sechenov First Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy Department, Moscow.⁵ MD, PhD, Full Professor of Anatomy, Department of Basic Medical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (UNIMAS)**Abstract:**

September 13 - 16, 2018, the 10th International Clinical and Applied Anatomy Symposium (ISCAA 2018) was held at the site of the Department of Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy of the Medical Faculty of Sechenov University. Russian scientists in a tense struggle won half of the honorary diplomas of the symposium, presenting bright, well-prepared and decorated, lectures and speeches. Confirmation of the leading position of Sechenov University among the medical schools of Russia is that among the 17 participants of the symposium who were awarded honorary diplomas - 6 are its representatives. Abstracts that have been selected by the Symposium Program Committee are printed in a special issue of the Morphology journal.

Key words: congress, medicine, education, human anatomy, iscaa

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INTRODUCTION:

September 13 - 16, 2018, the 10th International Clinical and Applied Anatomy Symposium (ISCAA 2018) was held at the site of the Department of Operative Surgery and Topographic Anatomy of the Medical Faculty of Sechenov University. The official language of this event was English. It was visited by more than 200 participants from 23 countries, both near and far abroad.

The symposium participants included representatives from Austria, Bahrain, Hungary, Germany, Greece, India, Iraq, Spain, Italy, Latvia, Macedonia, Malaysia, Moldova, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, USA, Turkey, Croatia, Czech Republic, South Korea, and Japan.

The last time such a representative scientific anatomical forum was held in Russia about half a century ago - D.A. Zhdanov 1970 in Leningrad organized and held the IX International Congress of Anatomists.

On September 12, 2018, within the framework of ISCAA 2018, on the basis of the Central Union Hospital of the Russian Federation, with the support of "Bard Company" was held a workshop at the topic "Live Surgery", which aroused great interest among the participants. Professor A. Protasov performed the operation "Plastics of an inguinal hernia in Liechtenstein" in the online broadcast. Professor N. Matveyev after a presentation on the topic "Actual issues of modern hernioplasty", the stages of the operation "Laparoscopic inguinal hernioplasty" were demonstrated online to the audience.

A similar workshop at ISCAA was held for the first time last year in Innsbruck. It is gratifying that the holding of clinical workshops within the framework of the symposium is becoming a good tradition and we hope that it will be continued at ISCAA 2019 in Madrid.

10th International Symposium of Clinical and Applied Anatomy

September 13-16, 2018 | Sechenov University | Moscow - Russia

Pic 1. Participants of the congress

Picture 2. Lecture at the congress

The ceremonial opening took place on September 13, 2018 and began with a minute of silence in memory to prof. L. Kolesnikov, academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences and the symposium's president who left us in August. By the last will of the deceased, sounded the song of F. Sinatra "My Way".

The dean of the medical faculty member of Russian Academy of Sciences, professor Kinkulkina M.A. in the welcoming speech conveyed congratulations to the participants from the honorary president of the symposium of the rector of the Sechenov University Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences Professor P.V. Glybochko and wished a success to the event.

Head of the department of operative surgery and topographic anatomy, professor Dydykin S.S. in his report told the participants of the symposium about the 260-year history of the I.M. Sechenov First

Moscow State Medical University (Sechenov University), about his best scientists, doctors and teachers. Dydykin S.S. also briefly highlighted the 150-year history of the Department of operative surgery and topographic anatomy of Sechenov University. Speaking next at the opening ceremony of the symposium, the oldest clinical anatomist professor Kagan I.I. (Orenburg) reported about trends in the development of clinical anatomy in the twenty-first century. The clinical anatomists were greatly interested in the presentation of the clinical surgeon-proctologist Professor Tsar'kov P.V., who spoke about the differences in the approach of anatomists and clinical proctologists to the anatomical rationale for surgical interventions in colorectal surgery. Lecture of Professor Tsar'kova P.V. was read at a high global level in recognition of all those present at the symposium of clinical anatomists. The opening ceremony of the symposium was completed by a lecture by Friedrich Paulsen (Germany) on the trends

in teaching anatomy and histology, in the present and in the future.

The opening of the symposium ended with a welcome buffet in the courtyard of the department, among flower beds, in a large tent, in the center of which stood a russian samovar (heated metal container traditionally used to heat and boil water in Russia) made by ice.

As part of the Symposium, the participants were given a great opportunity to share their knowledge with a wide audience of anatomists, surgeons, specialists from other clinical specialties and basic medical sciences, as well as young scientists and students.

The main purpose of the Symposium is to expand and strengthen scientific cooperation and interaction between specialists in the field of clinical and applied anatomy and surgery, as well as improving the status and public recognition of human anatomy as a fundamental medical science and its importance for medical education and health care.

The key scientific topics of this event were: clinical and applied anatomy, general surgery, plastic surgery, neurosurgery, traumatology and orthopedic surgery, new technologies in anatomy and surgery, tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, the teaching of morphological sciences. The Symposium program included lectures, oral and poster presentations in all areas of clinical and applied anatomy.

During the three working days of the symposium, the participants were able to get acquainted with a broad scientific program, which included 18 lectures, 82 reports, take part in poster sections that showed more than 100 posters, and also spend time on excursions and walks in hospitable Moscow and ride the steamer on the nightly Moscow River during the final gala dinner. All participants noted that a youth section was created in the symposium, in which young scientists and students could fully participate.

The greatest interest was aroused by lectures marked by honorary diplomas of the symposium. Their owners were a team of colleagues from Austria, who presented a fundamental study on the topic: "Nervus cutaneus femoris posterior: a nerve with full of surprises!" (Speaker Georg Feigl), as well as (speaker Rene Fortelny), who demonstrated the close cooperation of clinical anatomists and practical surgeons of the Austrian University. Lecture of the professor from Malaysia Kapitonova M.Yu. on the topic "Problem-based learning?" aroused admiration

not only among clinical anatomists, but also doctors of other practical specialties. The study of Russian surgeon-oncologist Tsarkova P.V. on the topic: "Discrepancy or misunderstanding of" "Gross Anatomy" "and in vivo anatomy in colorectal cancer surgery, which caused a heated debate.

Russian scientists in a tense struggle won half of the honorary diplomas of the symposium, presenting bright, well-prepared and decorated, lectures and speeches. Confirmation of the leading position of Sechenov University among the medical schools of Russia is that among the 17 participants of the symposium who were awarded honorary diplomas - 6 are its representatives.

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150th anniversary at the department of operative surgery and topographic anatomy in the year of the 260th anniversary of the Sechenov University meets the full of young creative forces and energy. Sechenov University has established itself in the international community of clinical anatomists as a reliable partner, conducting its research and teaching activities at a high global level.

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